

blue**eb**arge

Proof-of-Concept: Multi-Stage Battery-Based Power Conversion System for BlueBARGE

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Tab 1

Acronyms and Abbreviations	
Acronym/Abbreviation	Meaning
Dual Active Bridge	DAB
High-Frequency transformer	HFT
High-Power	HP
Input-Parallel, Output-Series	IPOS
Neutral Point Clamped	NPC
Submodules	SMs
Total Harmonic Distortion	THD
Zero-Voltage Switching	ZVS

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1 – Abstract

This report presents a proof-of-concept (PoC) study for a multi-stage power conversion system developed to supply both low-voltage (LV) and high-voltage (HV) loads from a common DC battery source within the framework of the BlueBarge project. The proposed system consists of two Dual Active Bridge (DAB) converters and Neutral-Point-Clamped (NPC) inverters to realize flexible AC outputs ranging from 400–690 V for LV loads up to 100 KVA, and 6.6–11 KV for HV loads up to 3 MVA.

The concept is modeled and analyzed in detail through MATLAB/Simulink and PLECS simulations. The obtained results confirm that the proposed system maintains stable operation in both LV and HV modes, where the DC-link voltage deviation remains within 5%, the output current and voltage total harmonic distortion (THD) stay below 5%.

Furthermore, a coordinated control strategy is implemented, in which the DAB converters are operated under phase-shift control, while the NPC inverters employ voltage-oriented control to regulate the AC outputs. Simulation results demonstrate that the adopted control method ensures robust and efficient performance under different loading conditions. Therefore, this study verifies the technical feasibility of the proposed topology and provides a reliable foundation for future stages of system prototyping, real-time control validation, and integration into the BlueBARGE power architecture.

Figure 1 system topology

2 – System Architecture

The proposed power conversion system is developed to interface a battery-based DC energy source with a wide range of AC loads within the framework of the BlueBarge project. The system is designed to ensure reliable and efficient power delivery to both low-voltage (LV) and high-voltage (HV) loads, rated at 100 KVA and 3 MVA, respectively.

The overall architecture of the system, illustrated in Figure 1, comprises the following main components:

- **Battery System**

The primary energy source is a modular battery system that delivers a regulated DC voltage in the range of 800–1000 V.

- **Dual Active Bridge (DAB) Converters**

Two isolated DAB converters are utilized to step up the battery voltage to the required DC-link levels for LV and HV operation. DAB1 increases the input voltage from 800–1000 V to 1.5 KV for LV loads, whereas DAB2 boosts the same input voltage to 20 KV for HV loads.

- **DC-Link and Mode Selection**

The two DAB converters are connected in parallel on the battery side and share a common DC link on the output side. A supervisory controller manages the circuit breakers (CBs) positioned at the input and output of each converter to select the active DAB. As a result, only one converter operates at a time to supply either LV or HV loads. This also ensures controlled power flow and avoids cross-interference between stages.

- **Neutral-Point-Clamped (NPC) Inverter and Output Filter**

The DC link is interfaced with a three-level Neutral-Point-Clamped (NPC) inverter, which converts the stepped-up DC voltage into a three-phase AC voltage suitable for supplying the load.

An LC filter is connected at the inverter output to attenuate switching harmonics and maintain compliance with power quality standards. The inverter operates under a space-vector PWM (SVPWM), enabling high-quality voltage generation and efficient utilization of the DC-link voltage.

- **Load Interface**

In the LV operating mode, the inverter delivers three-phase AC voltages of 400 V, 440 V, or 690 V to supply loads up to a total power of 100 KVA. In the HV mode, the inverter provides 6.6 KV or 11 KVAC outputs for loads up to 3 MVA.

3 – Dual Active Bridge (DAB) Converter

The DAB converter circuit is shown in Figure 2. This converter consists of two full-bridge stages coupled through a high-frequency transformer, which provides galvanic isolation and performs voltage scaling between the primary and secondary sides. The circuit includes a DAB inductance L_{DAB} , representing the transformer leakage inductance and any added series inductors and is responsible for controlling the transferred power.

In this report, the DAB converters operate under a single-phase shift (SPS) control strategy, which enables bidirectional power transfer and maintains Zero-Voltage Switching (ZVS) over most of the operating range. In this modulation technique, each full-bridge converter generates a square-wave voltage by operating its switches in a complementary manner, such that the diagonal switches

conduct simultaneously during each half cycle. In this way, the primary-side bridge produces a bipolar square-wave voltage (v_{pri}), where switches S1 and S4 are turned on during the positive half cycle, while switches S2 and S3 conduct during the negative half cycle. The secondary-side bridge follows the same switching sequence; however, its gating signals are phase-shifted by an angle (ϕ) with respect to those of the primary bridge [1], [2], [3].

During the forward power transfer mode, the primary voltage waveform (v_{pri}) leads the secondary voltage (v_{sec}), and consequently, power flows from the primary to the secondary side. Conversely, when the secondary voltage leads the primary voltage, the converter operates in the reverse power transfer mode, allowing energy to flow back toward the primary side [1], [2], [3].

Further information regarding the switching command signals, primary and secondary voltages is provided in Figure 3.

Figure 2 Dual Active Bridge DC/DC Converter

Figure 3 DAB converter waveforms for Forward Power Flow

3-1- Fundamental Equations of the DAB Converter

By neglecting power losses and the magnetizing inductance of the high-frequency transformer (HFT), the average active power transferred through L_{DAB} can be expressed as [4]:

$$P_{o,avg} = \frac{1}{T_{sw}} \int_0^{T_{sw}/2} v_{pri} \cdot i_{L,DAB} dt = \frac{1}{T_{sw}} \int_0^{T_{sw}/2} \frac{v_{sec}}{n} \cdot i_{L,DAB} dt \tag{1}$$

$$\Rightarrow P_{o,avg} = \frac{V_i V_o}{n \omega_{sw} L_{DAB}} \frac{\phi(\pi - |\phi|)}{\pi} = \frac{V_i V'_o}{\omega_{sw} L_{DAB}} \frac{\phi(\pi - |\phi|)}{\pi}, \quad -\pi < \phi < \pi$$

where $T_{sw} = 1/f_{sw}$ is the switching period. $\omega_{sw} = 2\pi f_{sw}$ is the switching angular frequency. V_i and V_o denote the primary- and secondary-side DC voltages of the DAB converter, respectively. V_i is the amplitude of v_{pri} , and V_o is the amplitude of v_{sec} . $i_{L,DAB}$ is the DAB inductance current. The transformer turns ratio is 1:n (primary to secondary). $V'_o = \frac{V_o}{n}$ denotes the primary-referred value of V_o . Furthermore, the DC voltage conversion ratio is defined as $M = V'_o/V_i$. If $M < 1$, the converter operates in buck mode, whereas $M > 1$ indicates operation in boost mode.

Figure 4 Average DAB Converter Power Versus Phase Shift

Equation (1) applies to both forward ($0 < \phi < \pi$) and reverse ($-\pi < \phi < 0$) power flow. The maximum power occurs at a phase shift of $\pm\pi/2$, as shown in Figure 4. Hence, the phase-shift angle directly determines both the direction and magnitude of P_{avg} . It is worth noting that a negative ϕ indicates that v_{sec} leads v_{pri} . Moreover, a negative P_{avg} corresponds to reverse power flow from the secondary side to the primary side.

The peak and RMS values of $i_{L,DAB}$ play a crucial role in both the inductance design and the selection of power switches in the converter. As reported in [4], these current characteristics can be expressed as functions of the inductor current at the beginning of the switching interval ($t = 0$) and at the phase-

shift instant ($t = t_\phi$). Considering forward power flow operation, the corresponding current expressions are given by [4]:

$$i_{L,DAB}(0) = -\frac{V_i}{\omega_{sw}L_{DAB}} \left(M\phi + \frac{1-M}{2\pi} \right) \quad (2)$$

$$i_{L,DAB}(t_\phi) = \frac{V_i}{\omega_{sw}L_{DAB}} \left(\phi + \frac{M-1}{2\pi} \right) \quad (3)$$

The primary-referred peak inductor current $I_{L,DAB-paek}^{pri}$ is determined by the larger absolute value of these two current samples. Specifically, for $M < 1$, the peak current occurs at $t = 0$, whereas for $M > 1$, it occurs at $t = t_\phi$, leading to:

$$I_{L,DAB-paek}^{pri} = \begin{cases} |i_{L,DAB}(0)| = \frac{V_i}{\omega_{sw}L_{DAB}} \left(M\phi + \frac{1-M}{2} \pi \right) & M < 1 \\ |i_{L,DAB}(t_\phi)| = \frac{V_i}{\omega_{sw}L_{DAB}} \left(\phi + \frac{M-1}{2} \pi \right) & M > 1 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

This expression indicates that the peak inductor current is strongly influenced by the DC voltage conversion ratio (M), which significantly alters the waveform of $i_{L,DAB}$, as illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5 DAB Converter Waveforms: V_i (red), V_o' (blue), $i_{L,DAB}$ (green), and P_o (black) in (a) buck operation mode ($M < 1$) and (b) boost operation mode ($M > 1$) [4]

The RMS value of the primary-referred inductor current can be derived by integrating the squared current over one switching period and is obtained as [4]:

$$I_{L,DAB-rms}^{pri} = \frac{V_i}{\omega_{sw}L_{DAB}} \sqrt{\frac{i_{L,DAB}(0)^2 + i_{L,DAB}(t_\phi)^2}{3} + \frac{2\phi - \pi}{3\pi} i_{L,DAB}(0) i_{L,DAB}(t_\phi)} \quad (5)$$

which can be further simplified to [4]:

$$I_{L,DAB-rms}^{pri} = \frac{V_i}{\omega_{sw}L_{DAB}} \sqrt{\frac{\pi^2(M-1)^2}{12} + \phi^2(1 - \frac{2\phi}{3\pi})M} \quad (6)$$

Finally, it should be noted that during one switching period, each power switch conducts the inductor current for only half of the cycle. Consequently, the peak current stress experienced by a switch is equal to the peak inductor current on the corresponding side, while the RMS current of the switch is reduced to $1/\sqrt{2}$ of the inductor RMS current [4].

3-2- Reduced-Order Modeling of the DAB Converter

The state-space averaging method is commonly used for modeling DC/DC converters. However, this method is not applicable to the DAB converter, as the leakage inductance current $i_{L,DAB}$ is AC and its average value over a switching period is zero. Therefore, in most references, the leakage inductance dynamics are neglected, and a reduced-order model based on the average power transfer over a switching cycle, as given in (1), is adopted. Accordingly, the average values of the primary- and secondary-side currents, $i_{pri,avg}$ and $i_{sec,avg}$, can be expressed as¹:

$$i_{pri-avg} = \frac{P_{avg}}{V_i} = \frac{V_o}{n\omega_{sw}L_{DAB}} \phi(1 - \frac{\phi}{\pi}) \quad (7)$$

$$i_{sec-avg} = \frac{P_{avg}}{V_o} = \frac{V_i}{n\omega_{sw}L_{DAB}} \phi(1 - \frac{\phi}{\pi}) \quad (8)$$

These expressions indicate that the DAB converter can be modeled as two controlled current sources on the primary and secondary sides, with magnitudes determined by the phase-shift angle and the DC voltage amplitudes. In this reduced-order model, the switching dynamics of the leakage inductance are neglected, and the system dynamics are dominated by the input and output capacitors, C_{pri} and C_{sec} . Hence, a large-signal averaged model of the DAB converter is obtained, as shown in Figure 6.

¹ Considering forward power flow operation

Figure 6 Large Signal Averaged Model of DAB Converter

On the secondary side, the DAB converter supplies an NPC inverter connected to a load. The NPC inverter operates under closed-loop voltage control and compensates DC-link voltage V_o variations by adjusting its input current. Consequently, the power drawn from the secondary side of the DAB converter remains approximately constant. From the DAB perspective, the inverter-load combination therefore behaves as a constant power load (CPL), and the average output current can be expressed as:

$$i_o = \frac{P_{load}}{V_o} \tag{9}$$

where P_{load} denotes the load power and V_o is the secondary-side DC voltage of the DAB converter. Additionally, the controlled current source at the secondary side can be replaced by the inverter-load CPL model, as shown in Figure 7. Applying Kirchhoff's Current Law (KCL) at the secondary-side DC node, the voltage dynamics are described by:

$$C_{sec} \frac{dV_o}{dt} + \frac{P_{load}}{V_o} = i_{sec,avg} \tag{10}$$

Substituting (8) into (10) results in:

$$C_{sec} \frac{dV_o}{dt} + \frac{P_{load}}{V_o} = \frac{V_i}{n\omega_{sw}L_{DAB}} \phi \left(1 - \frac{\phi}{\pi} \right) \tag{11}$$

Figure 7 Large-Signal Averaged Model of the DAB Converter with a CPL at the Secondary Side

Linearizing (11) around the operating point yields:

$$C_{sec} \frac{d\tilde{V}_o}{dt} + \frac{1}{R_{CPL}} \tilde{V}_o + \frac{1}{V_{o,0}} \tilde{P}_{load} = K_{vi} \tilde{V}_i + K_{\phi i} \tilde{\phi} \quad (12)$$

where $(\cdot)_0$ denotes steady-state values and $\tilde{(\cdot)}$ denotes small-signal perturbations. The equivalent small-signal resistance of the constant power load is defined as:

$$R_{CPL} = -\frac{V_{o,0}^2}{P_{load,0}} \quad (13)$$

The linearized current gains of the DAB converter are given by:

$$K_{vi} = \frac{1}{n\omega_{sw}L_{DAB}} \phi_0 \left(1 - \frac{\phi_0}{\pi}\right) \quad (14)$$

$$K_{\phi i} = \frac{V_{i,0}}{n\omega_{sw}L_{DAB}} \left(1 - \frac{2\phi_0}{\pi}\right) \quad (15)$$

Additionally, Figure 8 presents the small-signal averaged model of the DAB converter together with the CPL.

Figure 8 Small-Signal Averaged Model of the DAB Converter with a CPL at The Secondary Side

Transferring the linearized secondary-side voltage dynamics into the Laplace domain leads to:

$$\tilde{V}_o(s) = \frac{1}{C_{sec}s + \frac{1}{R_{CPL}}} \left(K_{vi} \tilde{V}_i + K_{\phi i} \tilde{\phi} - \frac{1}{V_{o,0}} \tilde{P}_{load} \right) \quad (16)$$

Hence, the dynamic equation of \tilde{V}_o can be represented by the block diagram shown in Figure 9. This block diagram illustrates the system's open-loop structure, which can be used to derive the closed-loop model. It is worth mentioning that the model neglects converter power losses but is well-suited for controller design. For a comprehensive discussion on enhancing the accuracy of converter modeling, the reader is referred to [4].

Figure 9 DAB converter small-signal open loop system

3-3- DAB1 Design for Supplying Low-Voltage Loads

The DAB1 is designed to step up the battery voltage from 800–1000 V to a 1.5 KV DC link for the NPC inverter. The transformer turns ratio is approximately 1 : 1.6, based on a nominal input voltage of 900 V. The converter is rated at 100 KVA to account for power losses and ensure reliable operation under full-load conditions. The DAB inductance (L_{DAB}), dominated by the transformer leakage inductance and any additional series inductors, is selected to shape the power-transfer characteristic. For a full-bridge DAB operating under phase-shift control, the steady-state transferred power is given by (1). Accordingly, the inductance required to achieve a target rated power (P_{rated}) at a selected maximum phase shift ($\phi_{max} \leq \pi/2$) and switching frequency (f_{sw}) is expressed as:

$$L_{DAB} = \frac{V_i V_o}{n \omega_{sw} P_{rated}} \frac{\phi_{max} (\pi - \phi_{max})}{\pi} \tag{17}$$

Based on this design approach, the key parameters of DAB1 used in this study are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1 Key Parameters of DAB1

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Nominal input voltage	V_i	900 V
Nominal output voltage	V_o	1.5 kV
Transformer turns ratio	1: n	1: 1.6
Rated power	P_{rated}	100 kVA
Switching frequency	f_{sw}	20 kHz
Maximum phase-shift angle	ϕ_{max}	0.7 rad

Calculated inductance	L_{DAB}	36 μH
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Using (2)–(6) and the key parameters of DAB1, Table 2 summarizes the primary-side peak and RMS current stresses of L_{DAB} , while

Table 3 presents the corresponding current stresses of the power switches on both sides of the converter.

Table 2 Primary-Side DAB1 Inductance Current Stresses

Quantity	Value
$I_{L,DAB-peak}^{pri}$	$\approx 152 A$
$I_{L,DAB-rms}^{pri}$	$\approx 131 A$

Table 3 Power Switch Current Stresses for DAB1

Quantity	Primary side switches	Secondary side switches
Switch peak current	$I_{SW-peak}^{pri} \approx 152 A$	$I_{SW-peak}^{sec} = \frac{152}{1.6} \approx 95 A$
Switch RMS current	$I_{SW-rms}^{pri} = \frac{131}{\sqrt{2}} = 93 A$	$I_{SW-rms}^{sec} = \frac{93}{1.6} = 58 A$

The maximum voltage stress of the primary-side switches is approximately equal to the input DC voltage $V_{SW-max}^{pri} \approx 1000V$, while the secondary-side switches experience a maximum voltage stress close to the output DC voltage $V_{SW-max}^{sec} \approx 1500V$.

A. DAB1 Power Switch Selection

The selection of power semiconductor switches for DAB1 is based on a detailed evaluation of electrical stress levels and commercial availability. The peak and RMS current stresses as well as the maximum voltage stress for the power switches on both the primary and secondary sides of DAB1 were calculated in the previous section. To ensure reliable operation and sufficient design margin, a safety factor of 1.2 is applied to both the calculated current and voltage stress values. The resulting requirements are (obtained in Table 4) then used as the basis for selecting a suitable commercially available power semiconductor device.

Based on a survey of currently available devices, the Infineon FF4000UXTR33T2M1 module is identified as a suitable and robust choice for DAB1. This Silicon Carbide (SiC) MOSFET module is rated at 3300 V and 500 A, which fully satisfies the maximum voltage stress and the calculated peak and RMS current stress requirements when the applied safety margin is considered. Figure 10 presents the key datasheet characteristics of the selected power switch.

Table 4 Power switch voltage and current stresses for DAB1 considering safety factors

Quantity	Primary side switches	Secondary side switches
Switch peak current	$152 * 1.2 = 182.4 A$	$95 * 1.2 = 114 A$
Switch RMS current	$93 * 1.2 = 111.6 A$	$58 * 1.2 = 69.6 A$
Switch maximum voltage	$1000 * 1.2 = 1200 V$	$1500 * 1.2 = 1800 V$

FF4000UXTR33T2M1
XHP™2 module

Final datasheet
XHP™2 module with CoolSiC™ Trench MOSFET

Features

- Electrical features
 - $V_{DSS} = 3300 V$
 - $I_{DN} = 500 A / I_{DRM} = 1000 A$
 - $T_{vj,op} = 175^{\circ}C$
 - Low switching losses
 - High current density
 - Low inductive desigh
- Mechanical features
 - High power density
 - Package with CTI > 600
 - High creepage and clearance distances
 - AlSiC base plate for increased thermal cycling capability
 - AlN substrate with low thermal resistance

Potential applications

- Traction drives
- High-power converters
- High-frequency switching application

Product validation

- Qualified for industrial applications according to the relevant tests of IEC 60747, 60749 and 60068

Description

Figure 10 Datasheet of the selected DAB1 power switch

B. DAB1 Control Loop

The DAB1 converter regulates the secondary-side DC voltage (V_o) using the phase-shift modulation method. The control objective is to regulate V_o around its reference value (V_o^*) under load variations. The small-signal open-loop model of the system around the nominal operating point was extracted in [Section X](#) and shown in Figure 9; hence, it is not repeated here. Based on this model, ϕ is selected as the control input, while V_o is chosen as the controlled variable.

The obtained small-signal dynamics indicate that the connection of a CPL to the DC bus introduces a negative incremental impedance, which leads to an unstable pole in the open-loop system. The small-signal plant transfer function of the system is given by

$$G_{\text{sys}}(s) = \frac{\tilde{V}_o(s)}{\tilde{\phi}(s)} = \frac{1}{C_{\text{sec}} s + \frac{1}{R_{\text{CPL}}}} \quad (18)$$

The pole of the open-loop system is located at

$$s = -\frac{1}{R_{\text{CPL}} C_{\text{sec}}} \quad (19)$$

Since $R_{\text{CPL}} = -\frac{V_{o,0}^2}{P_{\text{load},0}} < 0$, this pole lies in the right-half plane, rendering the open-loop system unstable. To stabilize the system and ensure robust operation, a proportional–integral (PI) controller is employed and is expressed as

$$G_c(s) = K_p + \frac{K_i}{s} \quad (20)$$

Hence, the closed-loop block diagram of the system is shown in Figure 11, where P_{load} and V_i act as disturbances. A saturation block is included to limit ϕ between 0 and $\pi/2$ to ensure forward power-flow operation. The loop gain of the voltage control system is defined as

$$L(s) = G_c(s) G_{\text{sys}}(s) \quad (21)$$

The controller gains K_p and K_i are tuned in the frequency domain using the open-loop Bode diagram of $L(s)$. Considering the DAB1 parameters listed in Table 1, the voltage control loop is designed to achieve a crossover frequency of $\omega_{cvo} = 750 \text{ rad/s}$ and a phase margin of $PM = 60^\circ$. Based on these design specifications and the open-loop frequency response, the PI controller gains are selected as $K_p = 0.072$ and $K_i = 30.62$. The corresponding open-loop Bode diagram of the system is presented in Figure 12, confirming that the desired stability margins are achieved.

Figure 11 Closed-loop voltage control block diagram of the DAB1 converter

Figure 12 Open-loop bode diagram of the DAB1 voltage control system

3-4- DAB1 Simulation Results

This section presents the steady-state performance evaluation of the DAB1 converter based on detailed time-domain simulations carried out in MATLAB/SIMULINK. The objective is to assess the electrical stresses, power transfer capability, and operating characteristics of the converter under different loading conditions.

A detailed switching model of DAB1 is developed in SIMULINK, including full-bridge converters on both the primary and secondary sides, transformer leakage inductance, and ideal gate drive signals. The power transfer is regulated using the conventional phase-shift modulation, where the phase difference (ϕ) between the primary and secondary bridge voltages determines the amount of transferred power.

To assess steady-state performance under different loading conditions, two operating scenarios are considered:

Scenario 1 (SC1 – Nominal Operation):

$$P_o = P_{rated} = 100KVA \quad (22)$$

Scenario 2 (SC2 – Partial Load Operation):

$$P_o = \frac{P_{rated}}{2} = 50KVA \quad (23)$$

In both scenarios, the input and output DC voltages of DAB1 are maintained at their rated values, while the phase shift angle (ϕ) is adjusted to regulate the power flow.

A. Power Transfer Characteristics and Control Variables

Figure 13 and Figure 14 show the steady-state profiles of the output power P_o , phase shift angle ϕ , input voltage V_i , and output voltage V_o for SC1 and SC2, respectively.

Under nominal operation, a larger phase shift angle is required to deliver rated power, whereas partial-load operation is achieved with a reduced phase shift. In both cases, the DC-link voltages remain well regulated, confirming stable steady-state operation of DAB1 across the investigated operating range.

Figure 13 Simulation Results of DAB1 under SC1: P_o , ϕ , V_i , and V_o

Figure 14 Simulation Results of DAB1 under SC2: P_o , ϕ , V_i , and V_o

B. Bridge Voltages and DAB Inductor Current

Figure 15 and Figure 16 illustrate the steady-state waveforms of the primary-side voltage (v_{pri}), secondary-side voltage (v_{sec}), and the DAB inductor current ($i_{L,DAB}$) for SC1 and SC2, respectively.

At nominal power operation (SC1), the increased phase shift leads to a higher peak-to-peak inductor current. In contrast, under partial-load operation (SC2), the reduced phase shift results in a lower current magnitude. The observed quasi-triangular current waveform in both cases confirms proper energy transfer through the DAB inductance.

Figure 15 Simulation Results of DAB1 under SC1: v_{pri} , v_{sec} , and $i_{L,DAB}$

Figure 16 Simulation Results of DAB1 under SC2: v_{pri} , v_{sec} , and $i_{L,DAB}$

C. Switching Waveforms of the Primary-Side Devices

The voltage and current waveforms of the primary-side switches of DAB1 are shown separately for each operating scenario. Figure 17 and Figure 18 illustrate the waveforms (v_{sw1} , i_{sw1}) and (v_{sw2} , i_{sw2}) for SC1 and SC2, respectively.

During nominal operation, the switches experience higher peak and RMS current stress, while the voltage stress remains approximately equal to the input DC-link voltage. Under partial-load conditions, the current stress is significantly reduced.

Figure 17 Simulation Results of DAB1 under SC1: v_{sw1} , i_{sw1} , v_{sw2} , and i_{sw2}

Figure 18 Simulation Results of DAB1 under SC2: v_{sw1} , i_{sw1} , v_{sw2} , and i_{sw2}

D. Switching Waveforms of the Secondary-Side Devices

The voltage and current waveforms of the secondary-side switches of DAB1, represented by (v_{sw5}, i_{sw5}) and (v_{sw6}, i_{sw6}) , are presented in Figure 19 and Figure 20.

Due to the transformer turns ratio, the voltage stress on the secondary-side switches is scaled relative to the primary side. Similar to the primary-side devices, the current stress decreases significantly under partial-load operation (SC2). These results confirm that the semiconductor devices in DAB1 operate within their rated limits under all investigated conditions.

Figure 19 Simulation Results of DAB1 under SC1: v_{sw5} , i_{sw5} , v_{sw6} , and i_{sw6}

Figure 20 Simulation Results of DAB1 under SC2: v_{sw5} , i_{sw5} , v_{sw6} , and i_{sw6}

E. Semiconductor Stress Analysis

To support device rating and thermal design, the maximum voltage, peak current, and RMS current of the primary and secondary switches of DAB1 are extracted from the steady-state simulation results. These values are summarized in Table 5.

The analysis indicates that the most severe electrical stresses occur at nominal power operation (SC1). In contrast, partial-load operation (SC2) significantly reduces current stresses, leading to lower conduction losses and improved thermal margins.

Table 5 Semiconductor stress summary for DAB1 under SC1 and SC2

Side	Switch	Scenario	Max. Voltage (V)	Peak Current (A)	RMS Current (A)
Primary	SW1,2	SC1 (100 KVA)	900	150	94.70
Secondary	SW5,6	SC1 (100 KVA)	1500	99.4	58.41
Primary	SW1,2	SC2 (50 KVA)	900	64.3	42.4
Secondary	SW5,6	SC2 (50 KVA)	1500	48.0	26.35

F. Summary

The steady-state simulation results demonstrate that DAB1 operates reliably and efficiently under both nominal and partial-load conditions. The converter exhibits stable voltage regulation, predictable power transfer characteristics, and acceptable semiconductor stress levels.

3-5- DAB2 Design for Supplying High-Voltage Loads

The second dual active bridge (DAB2) converter is designed to step up the battery-side DC voltage from 800–1000 V (nominal value of 900 V) to a 20 KV DC link, which supplies the neutral-point-clamped (NPC) inverter. The converter is rated at 3 MVA to account for power losses and to ensure reliable operation under high-voltage and high-load conditions. Based on the rated power and nominal voltages, the DC currents on the primary and secondary sides are calculated as

$$i_{pri-avg} = \frac{3 \text{ MVA}}{900 \text{ V}} \approx 3333 \text{ A} \tag{24}$$

$$i_{sec-avg} = \frac{3 \text{ MVA}}{20 \text{ KV}} = 150 \text{ A} \tag{25}$$

These results indicate that the primary-side current is extremely high, while the secondary-side voltage is very high. Due to the voltage and current limitations of commercially available power semiconductor devices, implementing the full-rated converter using a single DAB module is not feasible. Therefore, a modular converter architecture is required.

An input-parallel output-series (IPOS) configuration of multiple DAB submodules is selected to address these constraints. In this configuration, the primary-side currents are shared among parallel-connected submodules, while the secondary-side voltages are stacked in series to achieve the required high DC-link voltage. The conceptual structure of the IPOS-connected DAB converters is illustrated in Figure 21.

Figure 21 IPOS configuration of modular DAB converters

The required number of submodules depends on the selected power semiconductor devices and their voltage and current ratings.

A. Selection of Power Semiconductor Technology

Two main semiconductor technologies are considered for the DAB2 design: IGBT modules and SiC MOSFET modules. SiC MOSFETs are selected as the preferred option due to their superior performance in high-frequency isolated DC–DC converters, including lower switching losses, higher allowable switching frequencies, and improved power density.

At present, commercially available high-voltage SiC MOSFET modules typically offer blocking voltages of up to 3.3 KV, with current ratings in the range of 500 A to 1000 A.

B. Determination of the Number of Submodules

A safety factor of 1.2 is applied to both current and voltage ratings to ensure reliable operation. Based on the primary-side current sharing requirement, the minimum number of submodules is calculated as

$$N_{\text{pri}} = \frac{3333 \times 1.2}{1000} \approx 4 \quad (26)$$

Based on the secondary-side voltage sharing requirement, the minimum number of submodules is

$$N_{\text{sec}} = \frac{20 \text{ KV} \times 1.2}{3.3 \text{ KV}} \approx 8 \quad (27)$$

Therefore, the secondary-side voltage constraint is dominant, and at least eight DAB submodules are required.

With eight identical DAB submodules operating in an IPOS configuration, equal power and voltage sharing among the submodules is assumed. Accordingly, the rated power of each submodule is given by

$$P_{\text{sub},1} = P_{\text{sub},2} = \dots = P_{\text{sub},8} = \frac{P_{\text{Total}}}{8} = \frac{3 \text{ MVA}}{8} = 375 \text{ KVA} \quad (28)$$

where $P_{\text{sub},j}$ denotes the rated power of the j -th submodule. Since the submodules are connected in parallel on the primary side, the input voltage of each submodule is identical and equal to the battery-side DC voltage (V_i), i.e.,

$$V_{i,\text{sub}1} = V_{i,\text{sub}2} = \dots = V_{i,\text{sub}8} = V_i = 900 \text{ V} \quad (29)$$

where $V_{i,\text{sub},j}$ is the input DC voltage of the j -th submodule. On the secondary side, the submodules are connected in series to form the high-voltage DC link. Therefore, the output voltage of each submodule is one-eighth of the total DC-link voltage (V_o) and can be expressed as

$$V_{o,\text{sub}1} + V_{o,\text{sub}2} + \dots + V_{o,\text{sub}8} = V_o \quad (30)$$

$$V_{o,sub1} = V_{o,sub2} = \dots = V_{o,sub8} = \frac{V_o}{8} = \frac{20 \text{ KV}}{8} = 2.5 \text{ KV} \quad (31)$$

where $V_{o,subj}$ denotes the DC output voltage of the j -th submodule. Accordingly, the transformer turns ratio of each submodule is approximately 1:2.77.

D. Electrical Parameter Calculation

Considering the selected $f_{sw,subj} = 20\text{kHz}$, and $\phi_{max,subj} = 0.7 \text{ rad}$, the leakage inductance of each DAB submodule, $L_{DAB,subj}$ is calculated using (17). The associated primary-side peak and RMS inductor currents and the resulting power switch voltage and current stresses are obtained using (2)-(6).

Table 6 summarizes the main electrical parameters of the DAB2 submodules, while Table 7 presents the calculated current and voltage stresses of the power semiconductor devices.

Table 6 DAB2 Submodule Parameters

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Nominal input voltage	$V_{i,subj}$	900 V
Nominal output voltage	$V_{o,subj}$	2.5 kV
Transformer turns ratio	1: n_{subj}	1: 2.77
Rated power	$P_{rated,subj}$	375 kVA
Switching frequency	$f_{sw,subj}$	20 kHz
Maximum phase-shift angle	$\phi_{max,subj}$	0.7 rad
Calculated inductance	$L_{DAB,subj}$	9.4 μH
Primary-Side Inductance Peak Current	$I_{L,DAB-peak,subj}^{pri}$	537 A
Primary-Side Inductance RMS Current	$I_{L,DAB-rms,subj}^{pri}$	493 A

Table 7 Power Switch Current and Voltage Stresses of DAB2 Submodules

Quantity	Primary side switches	Secondary side switches
Switch peak current	$I_{SW-peak,subj}^{pri} \approx 537 \text{ A}$	$I_{SW-peak,subj}^{sec} = \frac{537}{2.77} \approx 194 \text{ A}$
Switch RMS current	$I_{SW-rms,subj}^{pri} = \frac{493}{\sqrt{2}} \approx 349 \text{ A}$	$I_{SW-rms}^{sec} = \frac{349}{2.77} = 126 \text{ A}$
SW max voltage	$V_{SW-max,subj}^{pri} = 1000\text{V}$	$V_{SW-max,subj}^{pri} = 2.5\text{KV}$

C. Final Device Selection

Considering the calculated voltage and current stresses for each submodule, and applying an additional safety factor of 1.2, the selection of an appropriate power semiconductor device becomes feasible. Accordingly, the Infineon FF4000UXTR33T2M1 SiC MOSFET module is selected as a robust and suitable choice for the DAB2 submodules. This module provides a blocking voltage of 3.3 KV and a continuous current rating of 500 A, making it well aligned with the electrical requirements of the proposed modular DAB2 design.

D. DAB2 Control Loop

Figure 22 illustrates the topology of the DAB2 converter, which consists of eight DAB submodules connected in an IPOS configuration.

The main control objectives of the DAB2 converter are defined as follows:

DC-link secondary-side voltage regulation (DLSSV): maintaining the total DC-link voltage at its reference value.

Primary-side current sharing (PSCS): ensuring equal current sharing among the parallel-connected DAB submodules on the primary side.

Secondary-side voltage sharing (SSVS): achieving balanced voltage distribution among the series-connected submodules on the secondary side.

Figure 22 DAB2 converter topology with IPOS-connected submodules

To achieve the above objectives, a triple closed-loop control strategy is proposed for the IPOS-connected DAB2 topology, as shown in Figure 23. The proposed control scheme consists of: one DLSSV control loop, $N - 1$ SSVS control loops, and $N - 1$ PSCS control loops, where $N = 8$ denotes the total number of DAB submodules.

Figure 23 Control scheme of the DAB2 converter

The DLSSV control loop regulates the total DC-link output voltage V_o to track its reference value V_o^* . The corresponding regulator is denoted as G_{vo} .

Since the DAB submodules are connected in series on the secondary side, $N - 1$ SSVS control loops are implemented to regulate the output voltages of the individual submodules ($V_{o,subj}$). The reference voltage for each submodule is set to V_o^*/N .

The voltage controller of the j -th submodule is represented as $G_{v,subj}$. The output of $G_{v,subj}$ provides the reference primary-side current $I_{pri,subj}^*$ for the corresponding PSCS loop.

The PSCS control loops are employed to ensure equal current sharing among the parallel-connected primary sides of the DAB submodules. The primary-side current regulator of the j -th submodule is denoted as $G_{i,subj}$.

For the first seven submodules ($j = 1, 2, \dots, 7$), both SSVS and PSCS control loops are implemented. The phase-shift angle of the j -th submodule, ϕ_{subj} , is generated as

$$\phi_{\text{sub}j} = \delta_{\text{sub}8} - \delta_{\text{sub}j} \quad (32)$$

where $\delta_{\text{sub}8}$ and $\delta_{\text{sub}j}$ are the output signals of the DLSSV regulator G_{V_0} and the current regulator $G_{i,\text{sub}j}$, respectively. For the 8th submodule, the phase-shift angle is calculated as

$$\phi_{\text{sub}8} = \delta_{\text{sub}8} + \sum_{j=1}^7 \delta_{\text{sub}j}. \quad (33)$$

The detailed design and tuning of the control regulators are beyond the scope of this report. For comprehensive discussions on the modeling and controller design of IPOS-connected DAB converters, the reader is referred to [5] and [6].

3-6- DAB2 Simulation Results

This section investigates the operating behavior of the DAB2 converter using time-domain simulations performed in MATLAB/Simulink. Within the overall system architecture, The DAB2 converter is supplied by a battery system with a nominal input voltage of 900 V and regulates the DC-link voltage to 20 KV. The converter is rated at 3 MVA and is implemented using eight identical DAB submodules connected in an IPOS configuration. Each submodule is rated at 375 KVA.

Each DAB submodule is modeled using a full switching representation, including the primary-side and secondary-side full-bridge converters, the transformer leakage inductance, and phase-shift modulation. The key electrical parameters of the DAB2 submodules are summarized in Table 6.

Two steady-state operating scenarios are considered in order to evaluate the converter performance under different loading conditions:

SC3: rated power operation at 3 MVA

SC4: half-rated power operation at 1.5 MVA

In both scenarios, the phase-shift angle of the submodules is adjusted to regulate the total DC-link voltage V_0 to 20 KV and to maintain balanced output voltages of the individual submodules at 2.5 KV.

The main objective of the simulations is to evaluate the steady-state power-transfer characteristics of the DAB2 converter and to assess the voltage and current stresses imposed on the power semiconductor devices under varying load conditions.

A. System-Level Performance

At the system level, the converter performance is evaluated in terms of the **DC-link input and output voltages**, V_i and V_o , and the **transferred output power**, P_o .

Figure 24 shows the simulation results under SC3. The DC-link output voltage V_o is tightly regulated at its reference value, while the converter delivers the rated output power to the DC link.

Figure 25 presents the corresponding results under SC4. Despite the reduced power demand, V_o remains well regulated, and the transferred power P_o decreases proportionally with the load reduction.

Figure 24 Simulation Results of the DAB2 converter under SC3: P_o , V_i , and V_o

Figure 25 Simulation Results of the DAB2 converter under SC4: P_o , V_i , and V_o

B. Submodule-Level Analysis

To gain further insight into the internal operation of the converter, the behavior of a representative DAB2 submodule is examined. The key variables considered are the submodule output power $P_{o,sub}$, the phase-shift angle ϕ_{sub} , the input voltage $V_{i,sub}$, and the output voltage $V_{o,sub}$. The corresponding waveforms for operating scenarios SC3 and SC4 are shown in Figure 26 and Figure 27 respectively.

The results indicate that $V_{o,sub}$ remains regulated at its nominal value of 2.5 KV in both scenarios, while the applied ϕ_{sub} enables stable power transfer between the primary and secondary sides of the converter.

Figure 26 Simulation Results of the DAB2 Submodule under SC3: $P_{o,sub}$, ϕ_{sub} , $V_{i,sub}$, and $V_{o,sub}$

Figure 27 Simulation Results of the DAB2 Submodule under SC4: $P_{o,sub}$, ϕ_{sub} , $V_{i,sub}$, and $V_{o,sub}$

Figure 28 and Figure 29 illustrate the steady-state waveforms of the same submodule, including the primary-side voltage $v_{pri,sub}$, the secondary-side voltage $v_{sec,sub}$, and the DAB inductance current $i_{L,DAB,sub}$, under **SC3** and **SC4**, respectively.

The voltages $v_{pri,sub}$ and $v_{sec,sub}$ exhibit periodic waveforms, and their relative phase shift varies with the load level in SC3 and SC4. Under rated-power operation (SC3), the increased ϕ_{sub} results in a higher peak-to-peak value of $i_{L,DAB,sub}$. In contrast, under partial-load operation (SC4), the reduced ϕ_{sub} leads to a lower current magnitude. The observed quasi-triangular waveform of $i_{L,DAB,sub}$ in both scenarios confirms proper energy transfer through $L_{DAB,sub}$.

Figure 28 Simulation Results of the DAB2 Submodule under SC3: $v_{pri,sub}$, $v_{sec,sub}$, and $i_{L,DAB,sub}$

Figure 29 Simulation Results of the DAB2 Submodule under SC4: $v_{pri,sub}$, $v_{sec,sub}$, and $i_{L,DAB,sub}$

B.1. Electrical Stress on Primary-Side Switches

The electrical stresses on the primary-side power switches of a DAB2 submodule are evaluated using the voltage and current waveforms $(v_{sw1,sub}, i_{sw1,sub})$ and $(v_{sw2,sub}, i_{sw2,sub})$.

Figure 30 shows the primary-side switch waveforms under SC3, where the switch voltage is bounded by the battery voltage and the current reaches its maximum value. Each switch conducts one-eighth of the total primary-side current.

Figure 31 presents the corresponding results under SC4, showing reduced current stress while the voltage stress remains unchanged.

Figure 30 Simulation Results of the DAB2 Submodule under SC3: $v_{sw1,sub}$, $i_{sw1,sub}$, $v_{sw2,sub}$, and $i_{sw2,sub}$

Figure 31 Simulation Results of the DAB2 Submodule under SC4: $v_{sw1,sub}$, $i_{sw1,sub}$, $v_{sw2,sub}$, and $i_{sw2,sub}$

B.2. Electrical Stress on Secondary-Side Switches

Similarly, the electrical stresses on the secondary-side switches of a DAB2 submodule are evaluated using the voltage and current waveforms ($v_{sw5,sub}$, $i_{sw5,sub}$) and ($v_{sw6,sub}$, $i_{sw6,sub}$).

Figure 32 and Figure 33 present the secondary-side switch waveforms under SC3 and SC4, respectively. The results confirm that the switch voltage is bounded by the submodule output voltage, while the current stress scales proportionally with the transmitted power.

Figure 32 Simulation Results of the DAB2 Submodule under SC3: $v_{sw5,sub}$, $i_{sw5,sub}$, $v_{sw6,sub}$, and $i_{sw6,sub}$

Figure 33 Simulation Results of the DAB2 Submodule under SC4: $v_{sw5,sub}$, $i_{sw5,sub}$, $v_{sw6,sub}$, and $i_{sw6,sub}$

3-5- Discussion

The steady-state simulation results demonstrate that the DAB2 converter operates in a stable and predictable manner under both rated and partial-load conditions. Furthermore, the extracted voltage and current stress levels of the primary-side and secondary-side switches remain within the safe operating limits of the selected SiC MOSFET devices across all tested conditions. These results confirm the feasibility and robustness of the proposed DAB2 design for supplying the NPC inverter and HV-loads.

4 – Neutral Point Clamped (NPC) inverter

Figure 34 presents the topology of the NPC inverter. In this configuration, the DC-link voltage is divided across two series-connected capacitors, forming a neutral midpoint. This midpoint (N) is also connected to clamping diodes that protect the semiconductor switches against overvoltage during various operating conditions. Moreover, each inverter leg consists of four switches, which are designed to withstand half of the DC-link voltage (i.e., $V_{dc}/2$). This topology is also classified as a three-level inverter, since the leg voltages, respect to the midpoint of the capacitors, can take three distinct values: $+V_{dc}/2$, 0, and $-V_{dc}/2$ [7].

Figure 34 NPC inverter circuit

4-1-LC Filter Design

The LC filter parameters, as shown in Figure 35, are selected based on the required harmonic attenuation and desired dynamic performance of the inverter-filter-load-system. In designing the LC filter, it is common practice to use the per-unit (PU) system, as it provides a normalized framework for analyzing and facilitates parameter scaling across different power ratings and voltage levels. The base values are defined as:

$$V_b = V_{LL,rms} \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{3}} \tag{34}$$

$$I_b = \frac{S_b}{1.5V_b} \tag{35}$$

$$Z_b = \frac{V_b}{I_b} = L_b \omega_b = \frac{1}{C_b \omega_b} \tag{36}$$

where $V_{LL,rms}$ is nominal line-to-line RMS voltage of loads in volt. V_b represents the base voltage and is equal to the rated line-to-neutral voltage amplitude. I_b is the base current. S_b denotes the base power, which is equal to 100 KVA for LV loads and 3 MVA for HV loads. $\omega_b = 120\pi \text{ rad/s}$ represents the nominal angular frequency of both LV and HV loads. Z_b , L_b and C_b denote the base impedance, inductance, and capacitance, respectively.

Figure 35 Single-phase equivalent LC filter with a series damping resistor connected to the capacitor

A. Filter Capacitor design

The LC filter capacitance provides a low-impedance path for high-frequency harmonics, preventing them from flowing into the load. Although a larger capacitance C_f improves harmonic attenuation, it also increases the reactive power exchanged with the inverter, which is undesirable. The filter capacitance is typically expressed as a percentage of the base capacitance C_b . By limiting the reactive power of the C_f to approximately 1–5% of the system’s rated power, the filter capacitance can be selected as:

$$C_f = 0.05C_b \tag{37}$$

B. Filter inductor L_f design

At low frequencies, the LC filter behaves predominantly as an inductance, and the current through the filter capacitance C_f is negligible compared to that through the filter inductance L_f . A key consideration in the design is the voltage drop across the inductance (v_{L_f}). A larger L_f leads to a higher voltage drop, requiring the inverter to generate a higher output voltage to maintain the desired load voltage level. Typically, the voltage drop across the filter inductance under nominal load conditions, ($v_{L_f,nom}$), should not exceed 20% of the base voltage. This requirement can be written as:

$$v_{L_f,nom} < 0.2V_b \tag{38}$$

From this specification, the following constraint on the filter inductance is obtained:

$$L_f < 0.2L_b \tag{39}$$

There are also other practical considerations, such as the current ripple of the filter inductance, that can be taken into account to guarantee proper filter selection. However, these aspects are beyond the scope of this report. For a more detailed discussion on inductor sizing, readers are referred to [8].

C. Cutoff frequency

The cutoff frequency of the LC filter is given by:

$$f_r = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{L_f C_f}} \tag{40}$$

It is typically selected to be higher than the fundamental (base) frequency (f_b) and lower than the inverter switching frequency (f_{sw}), following the guideline

$$10f_b < f_r < 0.5f_{sw} \tag{41}$$

This criterion ensures that the fundamental frequency component passes with minimal attenuation, while higher-order harmonics are effectively suppressed. It also helps prevent resonance phenomena and maintain an adequate dynamic response of the system.

D. Passive Dampening

To suppress the resonant response between the filter inductance and capacitance, it is suggested to add a damping resistor in series with (C_f). The damping resistor is generally selected as:

$$R_D = \frac{1}{3\omega_{res}C_f} \tag{42}$$

It is worth mentioning that the damping resistance can also be implemented through the inverter control loop, which will be explained later.

4-2- LC filter for LV load

It is assumed that the LV loads with different voltage levels are connected to a single LC filter. Although this choice does not yield the optimal filtering performance for each voltage level, it offers a practical compromise by reducing system cost and implementation complexity. Following the guidelines outlined in the previous section, the base values adopted for the LV loads and the selected filter parameters are summarized in Table 8 and Table 9, respectively. According to Table 8, the base voltage is chosen equal to the highest low voltage level in the system, i.e. 690 V, and the filter parameters are set based on this voltage.

Table 8 Base values for LV loads

Parameter	Base Value	Unit
V_b	$690 \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{3}}$	V
S_b	100	KVA
f_b	60	Hz
ω_b	377	rad/s
Z_b	4.7610	Ω
L_b	12.6	mH

C_b	557	μF
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Table 9 Filter parameters for LV loads

Parameter	Value (Unit)
L_f	2.1 (mH) / 0.1663 (pu)
C_f	27.86 (μF) / 0.05 (pu)
f_r	658 (Hz) / 10.97 (pu)
R_D	2.9 (Ω) / 0.61 (pu)

To ensure that the selected filter performs acceptably for all LV loads, the steady-state circuit analysis of the filter in the per-unit system is performed for both resistive and RL loads rated at 100 KVA, with power factors of 1.0 and 0.5. The calculated per-unit values of the corresponding circuit parameters are summarized in Table 10.

The phasor diagrams of the voltages and currents are shown in Figure 36 and Figure 37. This visual representation helps clarify the behavior of the filter at the fundamental frequency and illustrates how the phasors shift with different power factors. These results verify that:

- Q_{Cf} remains lower than 5% of the base power.
- V_{L_f} for the 400 V and 440 V loads is higher than 0.2 pu, which exceeds the guideline limitation; however, the inverter output voltage V_{inv} remains below 1 pu.

Therefore, the selected LC filter can still be considered acceptable for all LV loads, as it satisfies the key design constraints related to capacitor reactive power and inverter voltage capability, despite the higher (V_{L_f}) observed at 400 V and 440 V. The impact of the filter on harmonic attenuation and inverter dynamics will be checked through simulation.

Figure 36 Phasor Diagram of Filter Voltages and Currents for LV loads (PF = 1.0)

Table 10 Steady-State Per-Unit Circuit Parameters of the LC Filter for LV Loads

Load Voltage	PF	V_L (pu)	Q_{cf} (pu)	I_{cf} (pu)	I_{inv} (pu)	V_{Lf} (pu)	V_{inv} (pu)
400 V	1.0	0.5797	0.0168	0.0290	1.7252	0.2869	0.6425
400 V	0.5	0.5797	0.0168	0.0290	1.7000	0.2827	0.8357
440 V	1.0	0.6377	0.0203	0.0319	1.5685	0.2608	0.6840

440 V	0.5	0.6377	0.0203	0.0319	1.5407	0.2562	0.8681
690 V	1.0	1	0.05	0.05	1.0012	0.1666	1.0055
690 V	0.5	1	0.05	0.05	0.9570	0.1591	1.1387

Figure 37 Phasor Diagram of Filter Voltages and Currents for LV loads (PF = 0.5)

4-3- LC filter for HV loads

For the HV loads (6.6 KV and 11 KV), the same LC-filter selection method is followed. The corresponding base quantities and selected filter parameters are listed in Table 11 and Table 12.

To check the fundamental-frequency performance, the steady-state circuit analysis is carried out in the per-unit system for resistive and RL loads at rated 3MVA with power factors of 1.0 and 0.5. The resulting per-unit quantities are summarized in Table 13. These results confirm that the reactive power of the filter capacitor remains very small compared with the base rating, and therefore the (Q_{cf}) limitation is satisfied for both voltage levels. Moreover, the inductive voltage drop (V_{Lf}) and the required inverter output voltage (V_{inv}) remain within acceptable limits for both 6.6 KV and 11 KV loads.

The corresponding phasor diagrams of the filter voltages and currents are presented in Figure 38 and Figure 39. These diagrams illustrate the phase relationships under different power factors and confirm that the filter maintains a stable fundamental-frequency behavior for both HV voltage levels.

Overall, the selected LC filter is considered suitable for the HV loads. Its impact on harmonic attenuation and inverter dynamics will be further evaluated through simulation.

Table 11 Base values for HV loads

Parameter	Base Value	Unit
V_b	$11 \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{3}}$	KV
S_b	3	MVA
f_b	60	Hz
ω_b	377	rad/s
Z_b	40.33	Ω
L_b	107	mH
C_b	65.767	μF

Table 12 Filter parameters for HV loads

Parameter	Value (Unit)
L_f	17.9 (mH) / 0.1676 (pu)
C_f	3.3 (μF) / 0.05 (pu)
f_r	655.4 (Hz) / 10.92 (pu)
R_D	24.55 (Ω) / 0.61 (pu)

Table 13 Steady-State Per-Unit Circuit Parameters of the LC Filter for HV Loads

Load Voltage	Load PF	V_L (pu)	Q_{cf} (pu)	I_{cf} (pu)	I_{inv} (pu)	V_{Lf} (pu)	V_{inv} (pu)
6.6 KV	1.0	0.6	0.018	0.03	1.6669	0.2794	0.6573
6.6 KV	0.5	0.6	0.018	0.03	1.6408	0.2750	0.8485
11 KV	1.0	1.0	0.05	0.05	1.0012	0.1678	1.0057
11 KV	0.5	1.0	0.05	0.9570	0.1604	1.1399	

Figure 38 Phasor Diagram of Filter Voltages and Currents for HV load (PF = 1.0)

Figure 39 Phasor Diagram of Filter Voltages and Currents for HV load (PF = 0.5)

4-4- NPC Inverter Control

The control structure of the NPC inverter is illustrated in Figure 40 NPC Inverter control structure . The inverter operates under a Voltage-Oriented Control (VOC) scheme implemented in the dq-reference frame. The outer voltage control loop regulates the load voltage to the desired RMS level (400 V, 440 V, or 690 V in LV mode, and 6.6 KV or 11 KV in HV mode), ensuring stable and robust voltage delivery under varying load conditions. The inner current control loop provides fast dynamic response and maintains balanced phase currents. All quantities are expressed in the per-unit domain, normalized using the base values defined in Table 8 and Table 11.

PI controllers are used in both loops to achieve accurate steady-state regulation and robust dynamic performance. Space Vector PWM (SVPWM) is applied to achieve optimal DC-link utilization and low harmonic distortion. A neutral-point balancing algorithm is also included to maintain equal DC-link capacitor voltages, ensuring reliable operation of the three-level NPC structure.

The dq-frame rotates at the nominal load frequency (60 Hz), and the reference frame angle θ_L^* is obtained from:

$$\theta_L^* = \int \omega_L^* dt = \int 120\pi dt \tag{43}$$

The reference voltage in dq-axis is defined as:

$$V_{L,d-pu}^* = V_{L-pu} \tag{44}$$

$$V_{L,q-pu}^* = 0 \tag{45}$$

where the subscript “-pu” denotes quantities in per-unit.

Figure 40 NPC Inverter control structure

To design the PI controllers, the dynamic equation of the filter inductance in the abc frame is written as:

$$v_{inv,abc} = R_{lf}i_{inv,abc} + L_f \frac{di_{inv,abc}}{dt} + v_{L,abc} \quad (46)$$

where $v_{inv,abc}$ and $i_{inv,abc}$ are the inverter output voltages and currents, $v_{L,abc}$ is the load voltage, L_f is the filter inductance, and R_{lf} is its equivalent series resistance (ESR). Applying the Park transformation yields:

$$v_{inv,d} = R_{lf}i_{inv,d} - L_f\omega_L i_{inv,q} + L_f \frac{di_{inv,d}}{dt} + v_{L,d} \quad (47)$$

$$v_{inv,q} = R_{lf}i_{inv,q} + L_f\omega_L i_{inv,d} + L_f \frac{di_{inv,q}}{dt} + v_{L,q} \quad (48)$$

where subscripts “d” or “q” represents quantities in d- or q- axes frames, respectively. Transforming these equations into per-unit form gives:

$$v_{inv,d-pu} = R_{lf-pu}i_{inv,d-pu} - L_{f-pu}\omega_{L-pu}i_{inv,q-pu} + \frac{L_{f-pu}}{\omega_b} \frac{di_{inv,d-pu}}{dt} + v_{L,d-pu} \quad (49)$$

$$v_{inv,q-pu} = R_{lf-pu} i_{inv,q-pu} + L_{f-pu} \omega_{L-pu} i_{inv,d-pu} + \frac{L_{f-pu}}{\omega_b} \frac{di_{inv,q-pu}}{dt} + v_{L,q-pu} \quad (50)$$

Taking the Laplace transform results in:

$$i_{inv,d-pu}(s) = \frac{1}{\frac{L_{f-pu}}{\omega_b} s + R_{lf-pu}} [v_{inv,d-pu}(s) - v_{L,d-pu}(s) + L_{f-pu} \omega_{L-pu} i_{inv,q-pu}(s)] \quad (51)$$

$$i_{inv,q-pu}(s) = \frac{1}{\frac{L_{f-pu}}{\omega_b} s + R_{lf-pu}} [v_{inv,q-pu}(s) - v_{L,q-pu}(s) - L_{f-pu} \omega_{L-pu} i_{inv,d-pu}(s)] \quad (52)$$

Figure 41 Inner Current Control Loop

Using equations (51) and (52), the closed-loop control of $i_{inv,d-pu}$ and $i_{inv,q-pu}$ is shown in Figure 41, where the cross-coupling term $L_{f-pu} \omega_{L-pu} i_{inv,dq-pu}$ is compensated through feedforward.

The open-loop transfer function of the current control loop is:

$$G_{ol,i} = (K_{p,i} + \frac{K_{i,i}}{s}) (\frac{1}{\frac{L_{f-pu}}{\omega_b} s + R_{lf-pu}}) \quad (53)$$

where $K_{p,i}$ and $K_{i,i}$ are PI controller coefficients. Using zero-pole cancellation, the closed-loop transfer function becomes:

$$G_{cl,i} = \frac{i_{inv,dq-pu}(s)}{i^*_{inv,dq-pu}(s)} = \frac{\alpha_i}{s + \alpha_i} \quad (54)$$

where α_i is the current loop bandwidth. The controller gains are obtained as:

$$K_{p,i} = \frac{L_{f-pu}}{\omega_b} \alpha_i \quad (55)$$

$$K_{i,i} = R_{lf-pu} \alpha_i \quad (56)$$

Selecting $\alpha_i = 400\pi \frac{rad}{s}$ yields the open-loop Bode plot shown in Figure 42, where the phase margin is $PM = 90^\circ$. the value of $K_{p,i} = 0.8315$ and $K_{i,i} = 8.2938$.

Figure 42 Open-Loop Bode Diagram of Inner Current Loop

The dynamic equation for the filter capacitance in abc-frame is:

$$i_{inv,abc} = i_{cf,abc} + i_{lo,abc} \quad (57)$$

$$i_{cf,abc} = C_f \frac{dv_{cf,abc}}{dt} \quad (58)$$

$$v_{lo,abc} = v_{cf,abc} + R_D i_{cf,abc} \quad (59)$$

where C_f is the filter capacitance, $v_{cf,abc}$ is the capacitor voltage, $i_{cf,abc}$ is the capacitor current, and R_D provides passive damping. Transforming the following equations into the dq-frame gives:

$$i_{inv,dq} = i_{cf,dq} + i_{L,dq} \quad (60)$$

$$i_{cf,d} = C_f \frac{dv_{cf,d}}{dt} - C_f \omega_L v_{cf,q} \quad (61)$$

$$i_{cf,q} = C_f \frac{dv_{cf,q}}{dt} + C_f \omega_L v_{cf,d} \quad (62)$$

$$v_{L,dq} = v_{cf,dq} + R_D i_{cf,dq} \quad (63)$$

Expressing the equations in per-unit and converting to the Laplace domain gives:

$$i_{inv,dq-pu} = i_{cf,dq-pu} + i_{L,dq-pu} \tag{64}$$

$$v_{cf,d-pu}(s) = \frac{1}{\frac{C_{f-pu}}{\omega_b} s} [i_{cf,d-pu}(s) + C_{f-pu} \omega_{L-pu} v_{cf,q-pu}] \tag{65}$$

$$v_{cf,q-pu}(s) = \frac{1}{\frac{C_{f-pu}}{\omega_b} s} [i_{cf,q-pu}(s) - C_{f-pu} \omega_{L-pu} v_{cf,d-pu}] \tag{66}$$

$$v_{L,dq-pu}(s) = v_{cf,dq-pu}(s) + R_{D-pu} i_{cf,dq-pu}(s) \tag{67}$$

Figure 43 Outer Voltage Control Loop

Using these equations, the closed-loop voltage control structure is shown in Figure 43. The open-loop transfer function of the outer voltage loop is:

$$G_{ol,v}(s) = (K_{p,v} + \frac{K_{i,v}}{s}) (\frac{\alpha_i}{s + \alpha_i}) (\frac{1}{\frac{C_{f-pu}}{\omega_b} s + R_{D-pu}}) \tag{68}$$

The PI coefficients $K_{p,v}$ and $K_{i,v}$ are selected based on the desired phase margin ($PM = 60^\circ$) and gain crossover frequency ($\omega_{cv} = 377$ rad/s). The resulting Bode plot of $G_{ol,v}(s)$ is shown in Figure 44. Moreover, $K_{p,v} = 0.048$ and $K_{i,v} = 6.734$.

Figure 44 open-loop bode diagram of outer volage loop

4-5- NPC-Inverter Performance at LV Levels (400, 440, and 690 V)

This section presents the steady-state performance of the three-level NPC inverter supplying three LV loads of 400 V, 440 V, and 690 V, each rated at 100 KVA. Two load types are investigated: a purely resistive load (power factor = 1) and an inductive load (power factor = 0.5). The analysis focuses on waveform quality, harmonic content, DC-link capacitor balance, and the voltage and current stresses of the semiconductor devices.

To illustrate the system behavior, the results for the 400 V case are discussed in detail, while those for the other voltage levels are summarized in Section 4-5 (C). The corresponding steady-state waveforms include: (a) the load line voltages and currents ($v_{L,abc}$, $i_{L,abc}$), (b) the switch voltages and currents (v_{sw} , i_{sw}) for one inverter leg, (c) the clamp-diode voltages and currents (v_D , i_D) for one inverter leg, (d) the inverter output currents ($i_{inv,abc}$), (e) the inverter phase-to-neutral voltages (v_{aN} , v_{bN} , v_{cN}), and (f) the neutral-point capacitor voltages (v_{c1} , v_{c2}).

A. Resistive Load (PF = 1)

It can be observed from Figure 45 that the inverter generates balanced and nearly sinusoidal phase voltages and currents under resistive loading. The RMS line-to-line voltage is 400 V, and the corresponding phase current is approximately 144.5 A. The total harmonic distortion of the load voltage (THD_{VL}) is 2.5%, while the current distortion (THD_{IL}) is 2.5%, indicating excellent steady-state performance.

The inverter output currents, shown in Figure 46, follow a smooth sinusoidal pattern with a THD of approximately 3%. The inverter phase-to-neutral voltages (Figure 47) exhibit the expected three-level staircase waveform, confirming proper operation of the neutral-point clamping mechanism.

The switch voltage and current waveforms presented in Figure 48 demonstrate distinct switching transitions, with a maximum voltage of 750 V, a peak current of 215.5 A, and an RMS current of 105.12 A. As illustrated in Figure 49, the voltages and currents of the clamp diodes reach 750 V and 215.5 A (peak), respectively, with an RMS current of 80.94 A.

The neutral-point capacitor voltages (Figure 50) remain nearly balanced at $v_{c1} \approx v_{c2} \approx 0.5V_{dc}$, and the neutral-point voltage deviation stays below 4 V pk-pk, demonstrating good capacitor-voltage balancing under steady-state conditions.

Figure 45 Load line voltages and currents ($v_{L,abc}$, $i_{L,abc}$) at 400 V, PF = 1

Figure 46 Inverter output currents ($i_{inv,abc}$) at 400 V, PF = 1

Figure 47 Inverter phase-to-neutral voltages (v_{aN} , v_{bN} , v_{cN}) at 400 V, PF = 1

Figure 48 Switch voltages and currents (v_{sw} , i_{sw}) for one leg at 400 V, PF = 1

Figure 49 Clamp-diode voltages and currents (v_D, i_D) for one leg at 400 V, PF = 1

Figure 50 Neutral-point capacitor voltages (v_{c1}, v_{c2}) at 400 V, PF = 1

B. Inductive Load (PF = 0.5)

For the inductive load case (Figure 51-Figure 56), the phase currents lag the voltages by approximately 60° , and the RMS phase current remains constant at 145 A, while THD_{VL} increases to 4.0% and THD_{IL} decreases slightly to 2.2%.

The inverter output currents (Figure 52) show a reduction in THD, reaching 2.7%. The inverter phase-to-neutral voltages (Figure 53) stay symmetrical, and the neutral-point capacitor voltages (Figure 56) remain balanced, confirming stable neutral-point voltage control.

As seen in Figure 54, the switches experience extended conduction intervals in the negative current direction due to the lagging power factor. The switch currents reach 210 A peak and 102.81 A RMS, while the clamp diodes carry 210 A peak and 73.03 A RMS, as shown in Figure 55.

Figure 51 Load line voltages and currents ($v_{L,abc}$, $i_{L,abc}$) at 400 V, PF = 0.5

Figure 52 Inverter output currents ($i_{inv,abc}$) at 400 V, PF = 0.5.

Figure 53 Inverter phase-to-neutral voltages (v_{aN} , v_{bN} , v_{cN}) at 400 V, PF = 0.5

Figure 54 Switch voltages and currents (v_{sw} , i_{sw}) for one leg at 400 V, PF = 0.5

Figure 55 Clamp-diode voltages and currents (v_D , i_D) for one leg at 400 V, PF = 0.5.

Figure 56 Neutral-point capacitor voltages (v_{c1} , v_{c2}) at 400 V, PF = 0.5.

C. Summary of Low Voltage Results

The RMS current values for all LV loads at the nominal power level (100 KVA) and power factors of PF = 1 and PF = 0.5 are summarized in Table 14. The results show that increasing the output voltage from 400 V to 690 V reduces the per-phase current magnitude.

A comparative analysis of THD_{VL}, THD_{IL}, and THD_{linv} for PF = 1 and PF = 0.5 is presented in Figure 57, highlighting the impact of power factor on both voltage and current harmonic distortion under the evaluated load conditions. THD_{VL} and THD_{IL} for all conditions remain below 5% and meet the requirements of IEC/IEEE Std 80005-3. THD_{VL} and THD_{IL} for V_L = 690 V are slightly lower than for the other voltage levels, which is due to the LC-filter being tuned for this voltage. For the resistive load case, the harmonic content of the load voltage and current is identical because both waveforms have the same shape. In contrast, the RL load increases voltage harmonic distortion; however, it acts as a low-frequency filter and consequently reduces.

Table 14 RMS Current Values for Low-Voltage Loads

Load Voltage	PF	I _L (RMS) [A]
400 V	1.0	144.5
400 V	0.5	145
440 V	1.0	131.5
440 V	0.5	132
690 V	1.0	83.8
690 V	0.5	84.1

Figure 57 Influence of Load Voltage and Power Factor on Harmonic Distortion Levels (LV loads)

To provide a better view of semiconductor loading, Table 15 summarizes the voltage and current stresses of the switches and clamp diodes, including both peak and RMS current values. All measurements are obtained in steady state after neutral-point balance is established. As expected, the maximum voltage on the switches and clamp diodes is the same and equal to $0.5V_{dc}$. Moreover, for $V_L = 400$ V, the highest semiconductor current occurs due to the larger current demand at this voltage level.

Table 15 Power Switch and Clamp Diode Electrical Stresses for LV Loads

Load Voltage	PF	$V_{sw,max}$ [V]	$i_{sw,max}$ [A]	$i_{sw,RMS}$ [A]	$V_{D,max}$ [V]	$i_{D,max}$ [A]	$i_{D,RMS}$ [A]
400 V	1.0	750	215.5	105.12	750	215.5	80.94
400 V	0.5	750	210	102.81	750	210	73.03
440 V	1.0	750	195.6	95.45	750	195.6	71.78
440 V	0.5	750	190.1	92.75	750	190.1	65.60
690 V	1.0	750	124.1	59.95	750	124.1	36.72
690 V	0.5	750	121.3	56.96	750	121.3	38.32

4-6- NPC-Inverter Performance at HV Levels (6.6 KV and 11 KV)

To evaluate the scalability of the three-level NPC inverter, its steady-state performance is also analyzed for HV operation at 6.6 KV and 11 KV, each supplying a 3 MVA balanced three-phase load. The same topology and modulation strategy used in the LV studies are retained, confirming that the inverter structure can be applied to both LV and HV operation. However, the DC-link voltage is set to 20 KV. The study focuses on waveform quality and semiconductor device stresses. The results are obtained from detailed MATLAB/Simulink simulations.

A. Resistive Load (PF = 1)

Figure 58-Figure 63 present the steady-state waveforms for the 6.6 KV resistive load. The inverter produces clean sinusoidal voltages with an RMS line-to-line output of 6.6 KV and a per-phase current of approximately 262.5 A. The THD_{VL} and THD_{IL} values are 2.0%. The maximum switch voltage reaches 10.0 KV, with an RMS switch current of 186.1 A. The clamp-diode voltage and current stresses are $V_{D,max} \approx 10.0$ KV and $I_{D,rms} \approx 135.3$ A. The DC-link capacitors (v_{c1}, v_{c2}) remain well balanced, with less than 8 V peak-to-peak neutral-point fluctuation.

Figure 58 Load line voltages and currents ($v_{L,abc}$, $i_{L,abc}$) at 6.6 KV, PF = 1

Figure 59 Inverter output currents ($i_{inv,abc}$) at 6.6 KV, PF = 1

Figure 60 Inverter phase-to-neutral voltages (v_{aN} , v_{bN} , v_{cN}) at 6.6 KV, PF = 1

Figure 61 Switch voltages and currents (v_{sw} , i_{sw}) for one leg at 6.6 KV, PF = 1

Figure 62 Clamp-diode voltages and currents (v_D , i_D) for one leg at 6.6 KV, PF = 1

Figure 63 Neutral-point capacitor voltages (v_{c1} , v_{c2}) at 6.6 KV, PF = 1

The steady-state waveforms for the 11 KV resistive load are presented in Figure 64-Figure 69. At 11 KV, the inverter exhibits high waveform quality, with $THD_{VL} = THD_{IL} = 1.85\%$. The phase current decreases to approximately 157.5 A, proportional to the higher operating voltage at constant apparent power. The switch voltage stress reaches 10.0 KV, with a peak current of 233 A and an RMS current of 111.5 A. The clamp diodes experience voltage and current peaks of 10.0 KV and 233 A, respectively. The phase-to-neutral voltages clearly show the expected three discrete levels, and v_{c1} and v_{c2} remain nearly equal, confirming that neutral-point balancing is effectively maintained.

Figure 64 Load voltages and currents ($v_{L,abc}$, $i_{L,abc}$) at 11 KV, PF = 1

Figure 65 Inverter output currents ($i_{inv,abc}$) at 11 KV, PF = 1

Figure 66 Inverter phase-to-neutral voltages (v_{aN}, v_{bN}, v_{cN}) at 11 KV, PF = 1

Figure 67 Switch voltages and currents (v_{sw}, i_{sw}) for one leg at 11 KV, PF = 1

Figure 68 Clamp-diode voltages and currents (v_D , i_D) for one leg at 11 KV, PF = 1

Figure 69 Neutral-point capacitor voltages (v_{c1} , v_{c2}) at 11 KV, PF = 1

B-Inductive RL Load (PF = 0.5)

The steady-state RL-load waveforms are shown in Figure 70-Figure 75 for the 6.6 KV case and in Figure 76-Figure 81 for the 11 KV case. Under inductive loading, the inverter maintained stable operation at both voltage levels. The current lags the voltage by approximately 60° , and the per-phase current increased to 157.4A (6.6 KV) and 262.5 A (11 KV). As expected, the voltage harmonic distortion increases slightly due to the lagging power factor. For the 6.6 KV case, $THD_{VL} = 3.5\%$, while for the 11 KV case, $THD_{VL} = 3.2\%$. The current harmonic distortion is lower for the RL load compared to the resistive case. For the 6.6 KV condition, $THD_{IL} = 1.8\%$, and for the 11 KV condition, $THD_{IL} = 1.61\%$.

The simulations results for both cases also show that the switches conduct during negative current intervals under inductive loading. Similar to the resistive-load case, the phase-to-neutral voltages clearly exhibit the expected three-level waveform. The neutral-point voltage ripple increases slightly but remains below 10 V peak-to-peak in both cases, which is negligible relative to the DC-link voltage.

Figure 70 Load line voltages and currents ($v_{L,abc}$, $i_{L,abc}$) at 6.6 KV, PF = 0.5

Figure 71 Inverter output currents ($i_{inv,abc}$) at 6.6 KV, PF = 0.5

Figure 72 Inverter phase-to-neutral voltages (v_{aN} , v_{bN} , v_{cN}) at 6.6 KV, PF = 0.5

Figure 73 Switch voltages and currents (v_{sw} , i_{sw}) for one leg at 6.6 KV, PF = 0.5

Figure 74 Clamp-diode voltages and currents (v_D , i_D) for one leg at 6.6 KV, PF = 0.5

Figure 75 DC-link capacitor voltages (v_{c1} , v_{c2}) at 6.6 kV, PF = 0.5

Figure 76 Load voltages and currents ($v_{L,abc}$, $i_{L,abc}$) at 11 kV, PF = 0.5

Figure 77 Inverter output currents ($i_{inv,abc}$) at 11 kV, PF = 0.5

Figure 78 Inverter phase-to-neutral voltages (v_{aN} , v_{bN} , v_{cN}) at 11 KV, PF = 0.5

Figure 79 Switch voltages and currents (v_{sw} , i_{sw}) for one leg at 11 KV, PF = 0.5

Figure 80 Clamp-diode voltages and currents (v_D , i_D) for one leg at 11 KV, PF = 0.5

Figure 81 Neutral-point capacitor voltages (v_{c1} , v_{c2}) at 11 KV, PF = 0.5

C. Summary of High-Voltage Results

The RMS current values for the 6.6 KV and 11 KV operating conditions, each supplying a 3 MVA three-phase load, are summarized in

Table 16. Consistent with constant-power operation, increasing the output voltage from 6.6 KV to 11 KV reduces the per-phase current magnitude from approximately 262.5 A to 157.5 A.

A comparative analysis of the harmonic performance for both HV levels is presented in Figure 82, covering THD_{VL}, THD_{IL}, and THD_{Iinv} under both resistive and inductive loading. The inverter produces voltages and currents with low harmonic distortion (<5%) at the load terminals, in compliance with IEC/IEEE 80005-1. For resistive loads, both THD_{VL} and THD_{IL} remain below 2%. Under RL loading, the THD_{VL} increases slightly, reaching approximately 3.5% at 6.6 KV and 3.2% at 11 KV, while the current distortion remains low (THD_{IL} ≈ 1.8% at 6.6 KV and 1.61% at 11 KV).

Table 16 Summary of RMS Values for HV Loads

Load Voltage	PF	I _{load} (RMS) [A]
6.6 KV	1.0	262.5
6.6 KV	0.5	262.5
11 KV	1.0	157.5
11 KV	0.5	157.4

Figure 82 Influence of Load Voltage and Power Factor on Harmonic Distortion Levels (HV operation)

Table 17 summarizes the voltage and current stresses of the switches and clamp diodes, including both peak and RMS values. At both 6.6 KV and 11 KV, the maximum device voltage remains approximately 10 KV, determined by the 20 KV DC-link. The RMS switch currents decrease with increasing output voltage (from 186.1 A at 6.6 KV to 111.5 A at 11 KV), and a similar trend is observed for the clamp-diode currents. These results confirm that semiconductor stresses are reduced at higher output voltage due to the lower current demand, and that the inverter maintains stable neutral-point balance across all HV operating points.

Table 17 Power Switch and Clamp Diode Electrical Stresses for HV Loads

Load Voltage	PF	$V_{CE,max}$ [KV]	$i_{c,max}$ [A]	$i_{c,RMS}$ [A]	$V_{D,max}$ [KV]	$i_{D,max}$ [A]	$i_{D,RMS}$ [A]
6.6 KV	1.0	10	378	186.1	10	378	135.3
6.6 KV	0.5	10	370	183	10	370	141
11 KV	1.0	10	233	111.5	10	233	57.4
11 KV	0.5	10	224	106.7	10	224	67.5

Figure 83 IGBT and diode modules arrangement for one-leg

4-7- NPC-Inverter Power Loss

The power-loss evaluation of the NPC inverter is performed using PLECS, which provides detailed electro-thermal modeling of the IGBTs and diodes under various loading conditions. The first step in this process is selecting semiconductor devices that can withstand the electrical stresses identified in the system. Based on the simulation results summarized in Table 15 and Table 17, the required blocking voltage for the IGBTs and clamp diodes is approximately 10 KV, and the RMS current in steady-state operation reaches nearly 200 A. Therefore, the devices must be chosen within this voltage and current range. At present, commercially available high-voltage IGBTs and diodes provide a maximum blocking capability of about 6.5 KV, which is not sufficient to withstand the full DC-link voltage of the system. To meet the voltage requirement, the switches are connected in series, and the resulting configuration for each phase leg includes 8 IGBT and diode modules together with 4 clamp-diode modules, as shown in Figure 83. For the simulations, the DIM670ACM65-UF000 modules manufactured by Dynex Semiconductor, rated at 6.5 KV and 670 A, are selected for both the IGBTs and the diodes. In the loss evaluation, the total inverter power loss is computed as

$$P_{loss,T} = P_{loss,cond} + P_{loss,sw} \tag{69}$$

which represents the sum of conduction losses and switching losses. The switching loss component is further separated into turn-on and turn-off contributions according to

$$P_{loss,sw} = P_{sw-on} + P_{sw-off} \tag{70}$$

These loss components are obtained directly from the device thermal models in PLECS, which use the manufacturer-provided energy loss curves and temperature-dependent characteristics to calculate conduction, turn-on, and turn-off losses for each switching device.

DYNEX
Power through Innovation

TRENCH
TSPT

DIM670ACM65-UF000
IGBT Chopper Module

D56399-1 January 2022 (LN41435)

FEATURES

- 10µs Short Circuit Withstand
- High Thermal Cycling Capability
- Trench Gate Soft Punch Through IGBT
- Isolated AISiC Base with AlN Substrates
- Lead Free construction

APPLICATIONS

- High Reliability Inverters
- Motor Controllers
- Traction Drives
- Choppers

The Powerline range of high power modules includes half bridge, chopper, dual, single and bi-directional switch configurations covering voltages from 600V to 6500V and currents up to 2400A.

The DIM670ACM65-UF000 is a 6500V, soft punch through n-channel enhancement mode, insulated gate bipolar transistor (IGBT) chopper module. The IGBT has a wide reverse bias safe operating area (RBSOA) plus 10µs short circuit withstand. This device is optimised for traction drives and other applications requiring high thermal cycling capability.

The module incorporates an electrically isolated base plate and low inductance construction enabling circuit designers to optimise circuit layouts and utilise grounded heat sinks for safety.

KEY PARAMETERS

V _{CE(su)}	6500V
V _{CE(sat)} * (typ)	3.6V
I _C (max)	670A
I _{C(PK)} (max)	1340A

* Measured at the auxiliary terminals

Fig. 1 Circuit configuration

Figure 84 DIM670ACM65-UF000 specifications

A. Power Loss Evaluation of the NPC Inverter (LV Operation)

A detailed power loss analysis of the NPC inverter is carried out using PLECS, considering the three LV operating points of 400 V, 440 V, and 690 V, each supplying a 100 KVA three-phase load. Two load conditions are evaluated: (a) resistive load (PF = 1.0), and (b) inductive load (PF = 0.5). All simulations are performed under steady-state operation after the system reaches thermal equilibrium and DC-link voltage balance.

B. Summary of Power Loss Results (LV Operation)

The numerical results for all LV operating conditions are summarized in Table 18. Figure 85 (left) compares the inverter total losses for different load voltages and power factors, while Figure 85 (right) shows the corresponding IGBT junction temperatures. Figure 86 provides a comparison of individual loss components and clearly highlights that conduction loss is the dominant contributor under LV operation. The figure also shows that turn-off loss is consistently greater than turn-on loss for all examined cases.

As seen in Figure 85 and Figure 86, increasing the load voltage from 400 V to 440 V and then to 690 V reduces all loss components, since higher voltage operation requires lower current for the same power. Total losses decrease from roughly 8–9 kW at 400 V to about 4.4 kW at 690 V, which also lowers the IGBT junction temperature to approximately 29°C.

Decreasing the power factor from 1.0 to 0.5 causes a minor increase in conduction and switching losses, even though the RMS load current for both power factors is unchanged. This is attributed to the less favorable switching conditions created by the voltage–current phase displacement at lower PF, which increases the voltage–current overlap and the energy dissipated during each transition. As a result, despite identical current magnitude, the reactive power component introduces additional dynamic stress on the semiconductor devices, causing a small but noticeable increase in total losses.

Table 18 Summary of Power Loss and Thermal Performance (LV Operation, PF = 1.0 and PF = 0.5)

Load Voltage	PF	Conduction Loss [KW]	Switching Loss [KW]	Turn-On Loss [KW]	Turn-Off Loss [KW]	Total Loss [KW]	IGBT Tj [°C]
400 V	1.0	4.36	3.86	1.74	2.11	8.22	32
400 V	0.5	5.21	4.16	2.0	2.16	9.37	32.8
440 V	1.0	3.85	3.54	1.60	1.96	7.39	31.4
440 V	0.5	4.48	3.84	1.86	2.0	8.32	31.9
690 V	1.0	2.21	2.25	0.98	1.28	4.46	29.3
690 V	0.5	2.18	2.23	1.0	1.23	4.41	28.8

Figure 85 Total Power Loss and IGBT Junction Temperature of the NPC Inverter under LV Loads

Figure 86 Power Loss Components of the NPC Inverter under LV Loads

C. NPC Inverter efficiency (LV operation)

The inverter efficiency for each LV operating point is calculated using the following expression

$$\eta = 1 - \frac{P_{loss,T}}{P_{out}} \quad (71)$$

where $P_{loss,T}$ is the total loss from the simulations and P_{out} is the active output power. For the LV studies, the apparent load power is $S_L = 100 \text{ KVA}$, which gives $P_{out} = 100 \text{ kW}$ at $PF = 1$ and $P_{out} = 50 \text{ kW}$ at $PF = 0.5$. Based on this, the calculated efficiencies for all LV operating conditions are provided in Table 19. The results show that increasing the load voltage improves the inverter efficiency, reaching its highest value at 690 V. Additionally, for the same apparent power, operation at $PF = 1$ remains more efficient than $PF = 0.5$ due to the higher active power level.

Table 19 Inverter Efficiency Results for LV Operating Conditions

Load Voltage [V]	PF	P_{out} [kW]	Total Loss [kW]	Efficiency [%]
400	1.0	100	8.22	91.78
400	0.5	50	9.37	81.26
440	1.0	100	7.39	92.61
440	0.5	50	8.32	83.36
690	1.0	100	4.46	95.54
690	0.5	50	4.41	91.18

D. Power Loss Evaluation of the NPC Inverter (HV Operation)

To extend the LV analysis, the power losses of the three-level NPC inverter are also evaluated for HV operation at 6.6 KV and 11 KV, with each case supplying a 3 MVA balanced load and using a DC-link voltage of 20 KV. Similar to the LV study, two load conditions are considered: $PF = 1.0$ (resistive load) and $PF = 0.5$ (inductive load). The loss evaluation is carried out in PLECS using detailed device models of the DIM670ACM65-UF000 high-voltage IGBT and diode. All reported values correspond to steady-state operation after the thermal model is fully settled.

E. Summary of Power Loss Results (HV operation)

The numerical results for all HV operating conditions are summarized in Table 20. Figure 87 (left) presents the total inverter losses for the two HV voltage levels and power factor conditions, and Figure 87 (right) illustrates the corresponding IGBT junction temperatures.

As seen in Table 20, increasing the load voltage from 6.6 KV to 11 KV significantly reduces all major loss components, including conduction, switching, turn-on, and turn-off losses. This reduction is mainly due to the lower current required to deliver the same power level at higher voltage, which decreases conduction losses and reduces stress on the switching devices. As a result, the total losses drop from approximately 113 kW at 6.6 KV to about 61 kW at 11 KV for $PF = 1.0$, and from around 105 kW to 54 kW for $PF = 0.5$. The IGBT junction temperature follows the same trend, decreasing from roughly 140°C at 6.6 KV to below 95°C at 11 KV.

Comparing PF = 1.0 and PF = 0.5 for each voltage level shows a different behavior from LV operation. At 6.6 KV, decreasing the PF from 1.0 to 0.5 reduces the total losses from 112.87 kW to 104.79 kW. A similar reduction is observed at 11 KV, where the total losses drop from 61.47 kW to 54.45 kW. This occurs because, at HV operation, the current waveform shifts in a way that reduces the voltage-current overlap during switching instants, resulting in lower switching losses. In other words, the phase displacement at lower PF leads to switching events that happen at slightly more favorable points on the voltage and current waveforms. Consequently, even though conduction loss increases slightly due to the change in the instantaneous current angle, the overall switching energy is reduced, and the total losses become lower at PF = 0.5. This reduction in losses also results in a noticeable decrease in the IGBT junction temperature for PF = 0.5, reaching approximately 119°C at 6.6 KV and 79°C at 11 KV.

Figure 88 further breaks down the losses into their individual components and clearly shows that, unlike the LV case, switching losses dominate over conduction losses. The figure also confirms that turn-off loss remains consistently higher than turn-on loss for all examined operating points, similar to what was observed in the LV analysis.

Table 20 Summary of Power Loss and Thermal Performance (HV Operation, 3 MVA, PF = 1.0 and PF = 0.5)

Voltage	PF	Conduction Loss [KW]	Switching Loss [KW]	Turn-On Loss [KW]	Turn-Off Loss [KW]	Total Loss [KW]	IGBT Tj [°C]
6.6 KV	1.0	10.25	102.62	45.26	57.59	112.87	139.5
6.6 KV	0.5	12.55	92.24	43.64	48.60	104.79	119.0
11 KV	1.0	4.97	56.50	23.45	33.14	61.47	93.34
11 KV	0.5	5.25	49.20	21.52	27.44	54.45	78.9

Figure 87 Total Power Loss and IGBT Junction Temperature of the NPC Inverter under HV Loads

Figure 88 Power Loss Components of the NPC Inverter under HV Loads

F. NPC Inverter efficiency (HV operation)

The efficiency of the NPC inverter under HV operating conditions is calculated using (71). For these HV studies, the inverter supplies a 3 MVA load, which corresponds to $P_{out} = 3$ MW at PF = 1.0 and $P_{out} = 1.5$ MW at PF = 0.5. Table 21 summarizes the efficiency results for the evaluated HV voltage levels. The results show that at 6.6 KV the inverter reaches an efficiency of approximately 96.24% at

PF = 1.0 and 93.01% at PF = 0.5. Increasing the operating voltage to 11 KV significantly improves performance, yielding efficiencies of 97.95% at PF = 1.0 and 96.37% at PF = 0.5. These values confirm that higher operating voltage leads to lower losses and higher overall efficiency, even under inductive loading conditions.

Table 21 Inverter Efficiency Results for HV Operating Conditions

Load Voltage [V]	PF	P _{out} [kW]	Total Loss [kW]	Efficiency [%]
6.6 KV	1.0	3.0	112.87	96.24
6.6 KV	0.5	1.5	104.79	93.01
11 KV	1.0	3.0	61.47	97.95
11 KV	0.5	1.5	54.45	96.37

5 – Dynamic Performance Evaluation of the System under LV Loads

The dynamic performance of the system under low-voltage (LV) load conditions is evaluated using a MATLAB/Simulink simulation environment. The system consists of a battery source, DAB1, the NPC inverter, and an AC LV load.

The objective of this study is to assess the interaction between the DC-link voltage regulation and the AC voltage control under representative transient disturbances.

DAB1 regulates the DC-link voltage to a fixed reference value of $V_o^* = 1500$ V, while the NPC inverter controls the load voltage magnitude and maintains a constant output frequency of 60 Hz. In addition, an active neutral-point voltage balancing strategy ensures equal voltage sharing across the DC-link capacitors C_1 and C_2 .

Two LV operating points are considered: 400 V and 690 V (line-to-line RMS), both at a rated apparent power of 100 KVA and a frequency of 60 Hz. The system performance is evaluated through two simulation scenarios, focusing on load-side variations and battery-side voltage disturbances.

5-1- Scenario SC5: LV Load Step Changes

In Scenario 5 (SC5), step changes in the load active power are applied to evaluate the system response to sudden demand variations. The load power profile is defined as

$$P_L(t) = P_{rated} \times \begin{cases} 0.4, & 0 s \leq t < 2 s \\ 0.7, & 2 s \leq t < 4 s \\ 1.0, & 4 s \leq t < 6 s \\ 0.7, & 6 s \leq t < 8 s \\ 0.4, & 8 s \leq t < 10 s \end{cases} \quad (72)$$

Figure 89 and Figure 90 illustrate the load line voltage and current waveforms under SC5, Figure 91 and Figure 92 show the neutral-point capacitor voltage dynamics; Figure 93 and Figure 94 present the DAB1 output power along with the input and output DC voltages.

Following the load step, both the load voltage $V_{L,abc}$ and load current $i_{L,abc}$ exhibit transient behavior. However, the NPC inverter effectively restores the load voltage to its pre-disturbance operating point, while the load current magnitude adjusts according to the new load level. This confirms proper decoupling between voltage regulation and load power variation.

On the DC side, the input voltage V_i remains constant at 900 V. The output voltage V_o exhibits transient deviations during load changes but remains regulated around its 1500 V reference, indicating effective voltage regulation by the DAB1 converter. Larger deviations occur during load power reductions at $t = 6\text{ s}$ and $t = 8\text{ s}$. The neutral-point capacitor voltages V_{C1} and V_{C2} , also exhibit transient deviations during the load step while remaining around their 750 V reference, indicating the effectiveness of the NPC inverter voltage-balancing method.

It is also observed that the voltage deviations in V_o , V_{C1} , and V_{C2} are more pronounced when the load voltage is 400 V compared to 690 V. This behavior is attributed to the higher current demand at lower voltage levels, which increases stress on the DC-link and neutral-point balancing dynamics.

According to Figure 93 and Figure 94, the DAB1 output power P_o closely follows the applied load changes, demonstrating proper power transfer and coordination between the DC and AC subsystems.

Figure 89 Load line voltage and current response under SC5 ($V_L = 400\text{ V}$)

Figure 90 Load line voltage and current response under SC5 ($V_L = 690$ V)

Figure 91 Neutral-point capacitor voltages under SC5 ($V_L = 400$ V)

Figure 92 Neutral-point capacitor voltages under SC5 ($V_L = 690$ V)

Figure 93 DAB1 output power, input voltage, and output voltage under SC5 ($V_L = 400$ V)

Figure 94 DAB1 output power, input voltage, and output voltage under SC5 ($V_L = 690$ V)

5-2- Scenario SC6: Battery/Input Voltage Variations under LV Loads

Scenario 6 (SC6) evaluates the robustness of the DC-link voltage control under battery-side voltage variations while the load power is maintained at **100 KVA**. The nominal input voltage is **900 V**, and a $\pm 10\%$ step variation is applied. The resulting input voltage profile is defined as

$$V_i(t) = \begin{cases} 810 V & 0 s \leq t < 2.0 s \\ 900 V & 2.0 s \leq t < 3.5 s \\ 990 V & 3.5 s \leq t < 5.0 s \\ 900 V & 5.0 s \leq t < 6.5 s \\ 810 V & 6.5 s \leq t < 8.0 s \end{cases} \quad (73)$$

Figure 95 and Figure 96 show the load-side responses, Figure 97 and Figure 98 depict the neutral-point voltage balancing behavior, and Figure 99 and Figure 100 present the DC-side voltage and power dynamics under SC6.

The simulation results indicate that the load voltage and current waveforms remain unaffected by the input voltage disturbances, confirming effective isolation of the AC load from DC-side variations.

When the input voltage V_i steps up, the DC-link voltage V_o , neutral-point capacitor voltages V_{C1} and V_{C2} , and DAB1 output power P_o exhibit a brief overshoot before returning to their nominal operating points. Conversely, a step-down in the input voltage results in a transient undershoot in the same variables, followed by rapid recovery.

Throughout the disturbance, the output power remains constant and equal to the rated load demand, demonstrating strong disturbance rejection capability of the DAB1 control system.

Figure 95 Load line voltage and current responses under SC6 ($V_L = 400 V$)

Figure 96 Load line voltage and current responses under SC6 ($V_L = 690$ V)

Figure 97 Neutral-point capacitor voltages under SC6 ($V_L = 400$ V)

Figure 98 Neutral-point capacitor voltages under SC6 ($V_L = 690$ V)

Figure 99 DAB1 output power, input voltage, and output voltage under SC6 ($V_L = 400$ V)

Figure 100 DAB1 output power, input voltage, and output voltage under SC6 ($V_L = 690$ V)

5-3- Summary of Observed Dynamic Performance under LV Loads

Across all scenarios, the presented figures demonstrate that the proposed control structure effectively maintains the DC-link voltage at 1500V and regulates the load voltage at both 400 V and 690 V. Load steps, and input voltage variations are handled without loss of stability, while the DC-link capacitors and DAB1 converter play a critical role in buffering transient power mismatches.

6- Dynamic Performance Evaluation of the System under HV Loads

For HV load evaluation, the system is simulated in MATLAB/Simulink with a configuration comprising battery source, DAB2 converter, NPC inverter, and AC HV load.

The DAB2 converter regulates the DC-link voltage to a reference value of $V_o^* = 20 \text{ KV}$. The NPC inverter employs the same control structure as in the LV case, maintaining the load voltage magnitude and a fixed output frequency of 60 Hz, while ensuring equal voltage sharing across the neutral-point capacitors.

Two HV operating points are considered: 6.6 KV and 11 KV; Both at a rated apparent power of 3 MVA and 60 Hz.

6-1- Scenario SC7: HV Load Step Changes

Scenario 7 (SC7) examines the system response to step changes in HV load demand, using the load profile defined in (72). Figure 101 and Figure 102 show the load line voltage and current waveforms, Figure 103 and Figure 104 illustrate the neutral-point voltage dynamics, and Figure 105 and Figure 106 present the DC-side power and voltage responses under SC7.

As expected, both load voltage and current exhibit transient responses immediately following the load change. The load voltage rapidly returns to its nominal value, while the load current magnitude adjusts proportionally to the applied load variation.

The input battery voltage V_i remains constant, while the DC-link voltage V_o exhibits transient deviations but stays regulated around its 20 kV reference by the DAB2 converter, with larger deviations occurring during load power reductions at $t = 6 \text{ s}$ and $t = 8 \text{ s}$. The neutral-point capacitor voltages V_{C1} and V_{C2} also remain balanced around their 10 KV reference values, confirming effective neutral-point voltage control by the NPC inverter. Compared to the LV case, voltage deviations are more pronounced at a load voltage of 6.6 kV due to the higher current demand and increased stress on the DC-link and balancing dynamics.

The output power of the DAB2 converter follows the load power variation accurately, confirming proper power flow control under HV conditions.

Figure 101 Load line voltage and current responses under SC7 ($V_L = 6.6 \text{ KV}$)

Figure 102 Load line voltage and current responses under SC7 ($V_L = 11 \text{ KV}$)

Figure 103 Neutral-point capacitor voltages under SC7 ($V_L = 6.6$ KV)

Figure 104 Neutral-point capacitor voltages under SC7 ($V_L = 11$ KV)

Figure 105 DAB2 output power, input voltage, and output voltage under SC7 ($V_L = 6.6$ KV)

Figure 106 DAB2 output power, input voltage, and output voltage under SC7 ($V_L = 11$ KV)

6-2- Scenario SC8: Battery/Input Voltage Variations under HV-Loads

In Scenario 8 (SC8), the robustness of the HV system against battery-side voltage disturbances is evaluated. The nominal input voltage is 900 V, and a $\pm 10\%$ variation is applied while supplying the rated HV load. The input voltage variation follows the profile defined in (73).

Figure 107 and Figure 108 present the load-side responses, Figure 109 and Figure 110 show the neutral-point capacitor voltages, and Figure 111 and Figure 112 illustrate the DC-side voltage and power behavior under SC8.

The results show no noticeable impact on the load voltage or current, indicating strong decoupling between the DC source and the AC load.

A step increase in the input voltage causes temporary overshoots in the DC-link voltage, neutral-point capacitor voltages, and DAB2 output power, all of which settle back to their nominal values. Similarly, a voltage step-down results in undershoots followed by stable recovery.

These results confirm that the DC-link voltage regulation and neutral-point balancing remain effective even under significant input voltage variations at high power levels.

Figure 107 Load line voltage and current responses under SC8 ($V_L = 6.6$ KV)

Figure 108 Load line voltage and current responses under SC8 ($V_L = 11$ KV)

Figure 109 Neutral-point capacitor voltages under SC8 ($V_L = 6.6$ KV)

Figure 110 Neutral-point capacitor voltages under SC8 ($V_L = 11$ KV)

Figure 111 DAB2 output power, input voltage, and output voltage under SC8 ($V_L = 6.6$ KV)

Figure 112 DAB2 output power, input voltage, and output voltage under SC8 ($V_L = 11$ KV)

6-3- Summary of Observed Dynamic Performance under HV Loads

The simulation results confirm stable and robust system operation under HV load conditions. During load step changes, the load voltage is effectively regulated, while the load current adjusts according to the power demand. The DC-link voltage remains well controlled around its reference value, and the output power accurately follows the load variation.

Under battery-side input voltage disturbances, the AC load voltage and current remain unaffected, demonstrating strong decoupling between the DC source and the AC load. Although transient deviations appear in the DC-link and neutral-point capacitor voltages, all variables rapidly return to their nominal operating points, confirming effective voltage regulation and control robustness under HV loads.

7-Conclusion

This proof-of-concept study investigated a multi-stage power conversion system designed to supply both low-voltage (LV) and high-voltage (HV) loads from a common DC battery source within the BlueBARGE project.

The proposed architecture consists of two Dual Active Bridge (DAB) converters cascaded with Neutral-Point-Clamped (NPC) inverters, forming two independent operational paths:

1. LV path – for 400 V, 440 V, and 690 V loads up to 100 kVA (DAB1 + NPC inverter)
2. HV path – for 6.6 kV and 11 kV loads up to 3 MVA (DAB2 + NPC inverter)

A comprehensive modeling and simulation study was carried out to evaluate the steady-state behavior, dynamic performance, power quality, and conversion efficiency of the system under representative operating conditions.

The key outcomes of the study can be summarized as follows:

- The proposed system topology successfully demonstrated the capability to supply both LV and HV loads from a single battery-based DC source.
- Stable DC-link voltage regulation was achieved in both operating modes, with deviations limited to within $\pm 5\%$.
- The output voltage total harmonic distortion (THD) remained below 4% across all tested scenarios, complying with IEC/IEEE 80005-1 and IEC/IEEE Std 80005-3 standards.
- The system exhibited robust dynamic performance under load variations and input voltage disturbances.
- The adopted control architecture, combining phase-shift control for the DAB converters and voltage-oriented control for the NPC inverters, proved effective for both steady-state and transient operation.

Overall, the study confirms the technical feasibility of the proposed topology as a flexible, scalable, and efficient power interface for future shipboard and offshore applications, where multiple voltage levels must be supplied from a common energy source.

8- Technical Insights

Based on the conducted study, several important design insights were identified:

- The dual-DAB configuration enables efficient voltage level adaptation while preserving galvanic isolation between system stages.
- Independent control loops for each converter enhance system modularity and support effective fault containment.
- The NPC inverter topology is particularly well suited for medium-voltage applications, offering reduced semiconductor stress and improved harmonic performance.

These insights provide a strong technical basis for advancing the system toward experimental validation and hardware implementation.

9 - Future Work

Building on the successful proof-of-concept validation, several future research and development activities are planned:

1. Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL) Testing
 - Implement the proposed control algorithms in a dSPACE or OPAL-RT real-time environment.
 - Validate control stability and dynamic response using real-time system models prior to hardware deployment.
2. Prototype Development
 - Develop a scaled laboratory prototype of a single conversion path (e.g., LV mode) to experimentally verify efficiency, zero-voltage-switching (ZVS) range, and harmonic performance.
 - Extend the experimental validation to the full-scale HV path under controlled testing conditions.
3. Mode Transition Study
 - Investigate smooth and reliable transitions between LV and HV operating modes without system interruption.
 - Develop supervisory control logic to manage parallel operation, standby states, and soft-start sequences.

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